
Report on UK Data Service Computational Skills Survey: Current use, value and training needs

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Key points

- Skills transformation is now an organisation-wide priority.

Staff across all Directorates overwhelmingly agree that computational, data-centric and AI-enabled workflows will be essential to the UK Data Service's future. This is not a view held just by technical specialists: the belief is shared by staff in operational, user-facing, administrative and managerial roles. The Service has reached a collective recognition that digital capability underpins our long-term future. Training is not just about capability but about productivity and risk reduction: a matter of efficiency, reproducibility and operational resilience.

- There is strong willingness and readiness to upskill.

Engagement with the survey was exceptionally high (64 respondents; c.80% of the workforce). Almost all staff (94%) are ready to participate in training in the next six months, with clear expectations for practical, applicable skills that will directly improve their current work. This represents a major opportunity for whole-organisation uplift.

- Current skills usage is uneven, revealing latent potential and strategic risk.

While 75% strongly agree that computational skills are essential, only 41% use them daily and 31% use them rarely or never. Technical capabilities cluster in specific teams, creating pockets of high expertise alongside areas reliant on manual processes. This unevenness introduces fragility and constrains our efficiency.

- Demand for training is strongly aligned with the UK Data Service Strategy 2024–2030 and ESRC/UKRI expectations.

Staff requests cluster around AI/ML, coding (Python/R/SQL), cloud and architecture skills, reproducible workflows, metadata and interoperability, and automation. These mirror strategic priorities on digital maturity, responsible AI, and modern, cloud-based data service delivery.

- Staff are seeking applied, contextualised training – not abstract knowledge.

Free-text responses repeatedly emphasise the desire to automate routine work, improve efficiency, enhance user services, and adopt modern, reproducible workflows. People want to learn in order to do their work differently – not simply to expand knowledge.

- The Service requires structured, role-differentiated development pathways.

The current “individual course selection” is essential but by itself insufficient. The data show clear clusters of need and indicate that bespoke team-based training, expert-guided learning, and staged progression routes will be essential to achieving organisational transformation. Focused and targeted training will directly support delivery of the UK Data Service Strategy

2024–2030 and expectations from the ESRC and UKRI on digital maturity and responsible AI. Managers will need to actively guide, support and monitor training pathways.

- This represents a key opportunity for the UK Data Service.

The service has the opportunity to capitalise on high staff motivation to embed modern, automated, reproducible and AI-enabled ways of working. The current risks are of uneven capabilities, operational fragilities, and misalignment with expectations of a national data infrastructure.

The UK Data Service needs to consider this a strategic priority to create the internal structures, pathways and support to enable transformation. The survey makes clear that developing computational and AI capability is not an individual training issue but an organisational priority. Investment decisions, budget alignment, clear objectives and accountability will be required. The skills staff are asking for e.g. across automation, reproducible workflows, cloud and architecture skills, AI, data visualisation and so on, are now fundamental to how a modern data service must operate. Without coordinated leadership, capability will remain uneven across teams.

Staff are motivated and ready to upskill, but without a structured, Service-wide plan the UK Data Service risks missing a critical window to modernise in line with current expectations of data services. Senior leadership direction is therefore essential to align resources, set priorities, and ensure that training leads to meaningful, organisation-wide transformation rather than isolated individual development.

It is likely that other data services are facing similar issues and are at a similar inflection point in their training needs.

Introduction

This report presents the findings of the UK Data Service staff consultation on computational skills, conducted November-December 2024 as part of the UKRI funded grant Building Computational Capacity among Global Data Service Staff (UKRI302: UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure Programme). See the Appendix for the definition of computational skills. The consultation achieved a strong response rate, with 64 staff (around 80% of the workforce) participating. The results show that staff across all areas of the Service recognise the critical importance of computational skills to the organisation's future and are highly motivated to develop their capability. While there is already a strong foundation of technical expertise, the survey highlights variation across roles and identifies clear opportunities for targeted, role-specific training. The findings will inform future investment in professional development, helping to ensure the Service remains at the forefront of data innovation and delivery.

In November 2024, the UK Data Service invited all staff to take part in a consultation to understand the organisation's current and emerging data and computational skills. The consultation was designed to inform future workforce development and training priorities, ensuring that staff across all functions have the capabilities needed to meet the changing demands of data services work. The survey formed part of the UK Data Service's wider strategic objectives on upskilling and professional development in data and AI. It focused on identifying existing strengths, perceived skills gaps, and preferred approaches to learning and development. Specifically, the survey was designed to understand the priorities for training in computational skills for UK Data Service staff.

Methods summary

Survey design and participation

An online survey (see Appendix) was conducted via Qualtrics and included 21 questions covering four main areas:

1. Practical details: consent, role, and availability for follow-up interviews or training.
2. Future expectations: how staff view the importance of computational skills in future roles.
3. Current skills and practices: the tools and methods staff currently use and how often.
4. Training demand: preferred training formats, topics of interest, and perceived team needs.

The survey link was distributed to all UK Data Service staff by email, with two reminders to maximise participation.

A total of 64 valid responses were received, representing around 80% of the workforce, comfortably exceeding our target response rate of 70%. This high level of engagement reflects strong staff interest in the topic and commitment to developing capability across the Service.

The survey received ethical approval from the Proportionate University Research Ethics Committee, University of Manchester, 21/11/2024, Ref: 2024-21717-38168.

Data management and analysis

Responses were carefully reviewed and cleaned. Identifying information (such as names, emails, and departments) was removed before analysis, and all text responses were checked to ensure no individuals or institutions could be identified.

The de-identified dataset was analysed descriptively to understand the distribution of current skills, patterns of training needs, and differences between functional groups. All analyses were conducted on secure University of Manchester infrastructure, and the de-identified dataset will be deposited in a suitable data repository at the conclusion of the project for transparency and secondary research use.

Workforce roles and overlap

The survey captured the diversity of work across the UK Data Service by ascertaining whether they had a data role in data processing, data infrastructure, or an outward-facing data role (i.e. supporting data users or data producers, including training). If they did, staff were further classified into whether their roles were (a) data processing or data infrastructure, or (b) outward-facing role supporting data users or data producers. Some respondents were classified into both categories to reflect the multi-functional nature of their posts.

Role coverage across the workforce

The 64 survey respondents represent an engaged and data-literate population, but with varied depth of technical capability. Across the 64 respondents:

- 51 staff (80%) identified as working in a data role.
- 13 staff (20%) did not fall into either of the data-related categories. These are people in business operations, communications, impact, or administrative roles that provide essential service support but do not have data processing, data infrastructure or outward-facing data role as a major part of their role. We recognise that that some people in this category have some aspects of their role which involve organising or using data but this is not their main role.

Of the staff in data roles:

- 24 staff (47% of staff with data roles) are in a Processing / Infrastructure role.
- 17 staff (33% of staff with data roles) are in an Outward-facing data role.
- 10 staff (20% of staff with data roles) are in both types of data roles.

This distribution shows that most staff are directly engaged with data in some capacity.

The analysis highlights that to some extent this is a cross-functional workforce. 20% of staff with data roles combine technical or processing responsibilities with user-facing

responsibilities, reflecting the integrated nature of some data service delivery. These staff might benefit from learning opportunities that bridge domains rather than target a single specialism.

Current data and programming capability

By role:

The table below shows how programming experience differs depending on the breadth of roles that staff perform. The question asked was “What is the highest level of proficiency you have in programming languages (e.g. Python, R) commonly used for computational tasks”. Overall, 36% of respondents reported having no programming experience, 14% beginner, 30% intermediate, and 20% advanced. However, this distribution varies substantially by role combination.

Non-data roles (business operations, comms, impact, admin)

92% report no programming experience and 8% beginner. As expected, technical skills are minimal in this group, reflecting their organisational and administrative focus, although, we know that some of these staff have social science (or other) data backgrounds.

Processing / Infrastructure roles only

The most technically skilled group: 76% are intermediate or advanced (38% each).

Only 13% have no experience, suggesting that most members of this group work with code or computational tools as part of their job.

Outward-facing / User Support roles only

This shows a mixed skill profile: 41% intermediate, 6% advanced, and 35% no experience. This group includes people who mainly interpret, present, or explain data, or are in access or data producer training or user support, rather than building or automating systems.

Processing/Infrastructure + Outward facing/User Support roles

60% are intermediate or advanced, evenly split between levels (30% each) – a very mixed group of varying skill levels.

Table 1: Data roles by programming proficiency, row percentages

Role/Role combination	Programming proficiency: None	Programming proficiency: Beginner	Programming proficiency: Intermediate	Programming proficiency: Advanced	Programming proficiency: All
No data related role – business ops/comms/impact/admin	92%	8%	0%	0%	100%
Processing/infrastructure roles only	13%	13%	38%	38%	100%
Outward facing/user support roles only	35%	18%	41%	6%	100%
Processing/infrastructure + outward facing/user support	20%	20%	30%	30%	100%
All	36%	14%	30%	20%	100%
n	23	9	19	13	64

Another way of looking at this is to classify staff with multiple roles into both roles, i.e. count them twice, and then analyse by role. When we look at the data in this way (Table 2), it becomes clear that:

- Processing / Infrastructure staff show the highest concentration of intermediate and advanced skills (both 35%), as expected for operational and systems roles.
- Outward-facing/user support roles show greater diversity: around one-third intermediate, 15% advanced, but 30% with no experience.

Table 2: Data roles for data facing professionals by programming proficiency (individuals may be classified into more than one role), column percentages

Programming proficiency	Role: All data facing professionals	Role: Processing / Infrastructure	Role: Outward-facing/user support
None	22%	15%	30%
Beginner	16%	15%	19%
Intermediate	37%	35%	37%
Advanced	25%	35%	15%
Column percent	100%	100%	100%
n	51	34	27

This distribution suggests that while many already work fluently with programming tools, there remains a significant segment who rely on others for technical tasks or have low skill levels.

Table 3 shows how often staff are using computational skills, by role combination. See Appendix for the definition of computational skills, which is wider than coding skills. Across the whole sample, 41% use computational skills daily, while 31% use them rarely or never. This confirms that computational activity is widespread but unevenly distributed across roles.

- In non-data roles (business ops, comms, impact, admin), roughly a third never or rarely use computational skills, and none use them daily. About 30% use them weekly, suggesting some light engagement (e.g. using data tools for reporting or communications) but not sustained technical work.
- Those undertaking only Data Processing / Infrastructure roles: these are the most intensive users: 71% use computational skills daily. Very few (8%) report never or rarely using them. This confirms many of these roles are the technical core of the Service.
- Outward-facing / User Support roles: here we have a mixed profile with about 30% using skills daily, 30% rarely, and the remainder monthly or weekly. It is likely that for this group their computational engagement depends on specific tasks (e.g. training, documentation, or light analysis).
- Both types of data roles combined (i.e. processing/infrastructure + outward facing/user support): 40% use these skills daily, with 20% each in the other frequency categories. This suggests sustained but varied computational activity across this multi-functional group.

Table 3: How often computational skills are used by role/role combination, row percentages

Role/role combination	Never	Rarely	Monthly	Weekly	Daily	All
No data related role - business ops/comms/impact/admin	31	31	8	31	0	100%
Processing/infrastructure roles only	8	8	4	8	71	100%
Outward facing/user support roles only	6	29	24	12	29	100%
Processing/infrastructure + outward facing/user support	20	0	20	20	40	100%
All	14	17	13	16	41	100%
n	9	11	8	10	26	64

Value placed on computational skills

The survey reveals an extremely strong shared belief that computational skills are essential:

- 75% strongly agree and a further 23% agree that such skills are “essential”.
- Yet only 41% report using them daily, and around 31% use them rarely or never.

This gap between perceived importance and actual practice is a clear signal of latent demand: staff recognise the relevance of these skills but may lack time, confidence, or opportunity to integrate them fully into their work.

Perceived usefulness of upskilling

Attitudes to learning are overwhelmingly positive:

- 88% see learning new computational skills as useful in their current or future role.
- Only 5% are unsure and 5% view these as not useful.
- 94% report that they would be available for training in the next six months.

The responses to the open-ended training questions and the benefits those staff expect to see from training (see Section 7 below) reinforce this picture: respondents frequently link data/AI training to performance, efficiency, innovation, and future service delivery. They anticipate that data science and AI will be increasingly embedded in everyday operations.

As shown in Table 4, staff expressed a clear preference for flexible and accessible training formats, with online learning materials (selected by 50 respondents) and online live training events (48 respondents) emerging as the most popular options. These preferences indicate strong demand for formats that can be integrated around workloads while still offering structured guidance. Notably, over half the respondents also requested access to experts who can support their teams or provide individual guidance, revealing a need for practical, contextualised learning rather than generic content. While in-person training remains valued (28 respondents), the overall pattern is one of a varied offer: staff want a combination of asynchronous materials, live online sessions, and targeted expert support to help them apply new skills directly to their work. This should guide the ongoing development of a flexible, multi-modal training offer.

Table 4: Expressed preferences for training formats, UK Data Service staff (multi-choice question)

Training Format	Count
Online learning materials	50
Training event (online)	48
Bringing in an expert to guide teams/individuals	35
Training event (in person)	28
Other	5

Skills currently used

Current practices span varied computational and technical skills, as shown in the Table below:

Table 1: Skills used – all respondents (n=64) versus data-role staff only (n=51) (multi-choice question)

Skill category	Skill	All staff (%) (n=64)	Data-role staff (%) (n=51)
Core computational practices	Programming languages (Python, R, SQL, JavaScript)	64	78
Core computational practices	Making API requests	42	51
Core computational practices	Version control (Git/GitHub)	45	55
Data handling & communication	Data wrangling / cleaning	39	49
Data handling & communication	Data visualisation	39	41
Infrastructure & reproducibility	Cloud computing platforms (AWS, Google Cloud)	34	39
Infrastructure & reproducibility	Workflow automation	28	29
AI & advanced methods	Prompt engineering (e.g. ChatGPT)	31	28
AI & advanced methods	Machine learning	20	26
AI & advanced methods	Artificial intelligence (e.g. NLP, predictive modelling)	14	16
Specialist / less common	Big data processing (Hadoop, Spark)	9	12
Specialist / less common	Other (e.g. GenAI, metadata schemata, DevOps, Docker, Kubernetes)	9	10
No use	None of the above	20	14

The most widely used skills among data-role staff are programming (78%), version control (55%), data wrangling (49%), APIs (51%), and cloud computing platforms (39%). Some skills and methods are present but not dominant: Machine Learning (26%), Workflow Automation (29%) and AI (specified as e.g. natural language processing, predictive modelling) (16%), are

present but not dominant. These might present opportunities for targeted expansion of skills. Prompt engineering is already non-trivial (28% of data-role staff), suggesting demand for responsible AI and evaluation practices. A non-trivial minority report no use of these skills. Of the 41 respondents who reported using programming languages, 22% considered themselves to be beginners, 47% intermediate and 32% advanced.

The situation is (as expected) very different for non-data staff, only 7 of whom report using any of these skills (although one person reported using 8 different computational skills). Generally speaking, staff outside data roles make very limited use of these tools, with only small numbers reporting workflow automation (3), cloud platforms (2), or data visualisation (4). The key crossover area between the two groups is prompt engineering, used by 14 staff in data roles and 6 outside them, reflecting the broader uptake of generative AI across the Service. The substantial divergence in technical practice between staff with and without data responsibilities highlights the importance of differentiated training pathways and targeted support to meet these distinct needs.

What training do people want?

The UK Data Service Staff Training Survey included open-text questions asking staff what training would support their work with data and digital tools. We analysed these responses in NVivo 15, consolidating answers into key themes, and compared patterns across managers and staff role groups. The analysis provides strong evidence of a clear and consistent desire for skills development direction from the workforce. People want future-proofing, not just tools. A high-level word cloud shows the key themes that emerged from the analysis, with the dominance of AI, machine [learning], Python, SQL, automation, data security, cloud computing and visualisation. It also indicates many words that signal the interest of staff in efficient application of skills, including basic management, genAI, and tools. Finally, it illustrates the broad remit for training needs with some more niche areas mentioned by fewer people. This cloud confirms that this isn't a casual interest but that people want to adopt professional computational workflows.

What staff are asking for

The codebook showing all themes, with descriptions of those themes and counts of coded data, is in the Appendix. Summarising these, six clusters account for the majority of requests, as shown in Figure 2. These themes reflect a broad spectrum of expertise. While some requests are basic (e.g. for orientation or awareness), others are advanced (e.g. for DevOps, Kubernetes). The implications for the Service are that we have multiple learner-personas, and cannot treat ‘computational upskilling’ as one audience.

It is important also to note that the two most frequently requested areas, “AI and Machine Learning” and “Prompt Engineering and LLMs”, are not discrete skills, but are rather umbrella categories that cut across multiple technical and organisational competencies.

From the open text coding (see codebook in the Appendix), these themes include:

- automation of routine processes
- understanding model limitations, bias and ethics
- using AI to assist with data analysis and cleaning
- integrating AI tools into existing workflows
- using AI to write or generate code (Python, SQL, R)
- using LLMs to support documentation, reporting, or user support
- developing judgement around AI.

The coding references and survey context (e.g. answers to what benefits people expect or hope for from training) make it clear that staff are asking not just to ‘learn AI’ but asking for training in how to apply AI in the context of their own work, to automate processes, improve efficiency, and change how work is done. These codes in particular intersect with other themes such as Python/R/Coding, Workflow automation/APIs/reproducibility, and Data architecture/ databases/cloud – all suggesting that AI demand is tied to practical transformation. This suggests that the survey responses show that “AI & Machine Learning” and “Prompt Engineering & LLMs” are gateway concepts; when staff mention them, they are implicitly asking for a constellation of skills e.g. automation, coding, reproducible workflows, data architecture and governance, and not a one-off training course.

Figure 2: Percentage coverage of training request themes from open text responses (NVivo analysis). AI, prompt engineering and coding represent the highest demand.

1. *Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning*: including generative AI, automation of routine tasks, applying AI to data analysis, and developing AI literacy. This demonstrates clear organisational demand for capability building.
2. *Prompt engineering and effective use of tools like ChatGPT/Copilot*: practical skills for integrating AI into everyday workflows – people want to use AI effectively in daily work.
3. *Programming skills and coding* (e.g. Python, R). Programming literacy is seen as a core enabling skill.
4. *Database and data architecture skills*: like SQL, cloud environments, interoperability, metadata and ontologies. There was substantive demand for training in managing data infrastructure.
5. *Workflow automation and reproducibility*: e.g. Git/version control, scripting, use of APIs, DevOps, pipeline design. This is not just interest, but is also driven by workload and desire for efficiency.
6. *Data visualisation and UX*: improving communication of insights for management and users.

These themes collectively signal a desire to work in a more automated, computational way — prioritising efficiency, interoperability, quality control and reproducibility.

Beyond this, two other important messages emerge:

- Some responses express not a specific skill, but uncertainty, namely the theme *Need help to understand what I don't know*. This indicates that a traditional “catalogue of courses” model will not meet need. Staff will require structured pathways, guidance on

where to start, and visible progression routes, particularly for those without prior coding or computational experience.

- Training needs reflect strategic risk, namely the themes: data security; interoperability, metadata, ontologies; workflow reproducibility; and automation. These are foundational requirements for a modern data service – not simply “nice to have”. Staff are explicitly asking for training that reduces fragility, improves reproducibility, and reduces reliance on individual tacit knowledge.

Patterns by role group

NVivo matrix queries show fairly clear differentiation by role group. The frequency counts for requested training are shown in Table 6. This distinguishes those in Data Processing and Infrastructure Roles, those in Data Outward-facing or User Support Roles, and those in support roles that are not data focused.

Staff in data processing and infrastructure roles most frequently request training in coding, data architecture, reproducible workflows and system-level capabilities. User-facing and data support roles place greater emphasis on applied AI, automation, data visualisation and user experience, reflecting their interface with researchers and stakeholders.

Importantly, AI and prompt engineering appear across role groups, but as discussed above are likely to reflect different underlying needs and applications. Overall, the pattern indicates role-specific training requirements aligned to organisational function that nonetheless point in a shared strategic direction towards more automated, computational and AI-enabled ways of working.

Table 2: Training topics requested by role group (frequency of mentions)

Training theme	Data processing & infrastructure roles	User-facing / support data roles	Non-data operational roles
AI, automation & applied AI			
AI and machine learning	12	12	9
Prompt engineering and LLMs	10	11	9
Automation of workflows	4	6	8
Core computational & analytical skills			
Python, R and other coding languages	9	12	2
Statistical analysis skills	0	2	1

Training theme	Data processing & infrastructure roles	User-facing / support data roles	Non-data operational roles
Qualitative data analysis (NVivo)	0	2	0
Data integration, infrastructure & governance			
Database design, data architecture, SQL			
APIs and data integration	2	2	1
Metadata, semantics, ontologies, interoperability	5	1	0
Ethical issues and data governance	2	1	0
Data security	4	1	0
Workflow reproducibility	4	9	3
User experience & communication			
Data visualisation	1	5	3
UX, web development and accessibility	1	3	3
Advanced / specialist areas			
Full-stack application development	7	3	0
Big data methods	1	1	0
Geospatial analysis	1	2	0
Orientation and uncertainty			
Need help to understand what I don't know	1	5	2

Notes:

- *NVivo coding of open-text responses; respondents could mention multiple topics.*
- *Frequencies indicate the number of respondents in each role group who mentioned the topic.*
- *Zero values reflect absence of mentions, not absence of relevance.*

In summary, what do UK Data Service staff want?

Table 7: What do UK Data Service staff want training in and for?

Group	Most requested areas	What this indicates
Data infrastructure roles	SQL, architecture, cloud, APIs, metadata/ontologies, security, full stack development	Staff want to be more efficient, and improve the resilience and interoperability of our data systems.
User-facing data support roles	Data visualisation, UX/web, analytical skills, prompt engineering, automation	Staff want to improve the experience and efficiency of user support/client interaction. They want to understand the landscape better, and want routes towards confidence and digital capability.
Non-data operational roles	AI literacy and entry-level coding orientation	Staff want to automate their routine tasks and build data visualisation skills.

Patterns by managers

Staff are asking to build the systems; managers seem to be asking to understand them well enough to lead within them. As Table 8 shows, managers did not express interest in the more technical tasks, but did express interest in automation, data visualisation, and interoperability. Some need help to understand what they do not know, and they were more likely than non-managers to express an interest in prompt engineering and LLMs.

Table 3: Patterns of manager requests for training

Topic	Non-managers (n=40)	Managers (n=24)
AI and Machine Learning	13	13
APIs and Data Integration	3	1
Automation	8	8
Big Data	2	0
Data Security	4	0
Data Visualisation	4	4
Ethical Issues and Data Governance	2	0
Full stack application development	7	0

Geospatial analysis	3	0
Metadata, Semantics and Ontologies, Interoperability	2	4
Need help to understand what I don't know	4	4
Prompt Engineering and LLMs	10	15
Python, R, other coding languages	13	7
Qualitative data; NVivo	2	0
Statistical analysis skills	2	1
UX, website development, accessibility	4	3
Workflow Reproducibility	7	6

What this means for the UK Data Service (strategically)

The survey reveals an organisational shift toward computational working, end-to-end digital workflows, automation and AI-supported processes, and reproducibility and reduction of operational risk. We need to invest in how to get there.

For the purposes of this report, we cannot provide analysis by Directorate as all identifying information (including department and institution) was removed from the database before analysis. However, the survey indicates a clear need for each Directorate to have a training plan that meets the needs of their own staff in meaningful ways. As the above analysis shows, this will undoubtedly vary from team to team, but it is very likely insufficient to simply give staff access to external resources for them to choose from. Some training will likely need to be bespoke to teams, and the survey has revealed that it is very important that staff can see immediate applicability to their own work and workflows, which is unlikely to be provided by generic or external courses. Also, there may well be “team demand” where bringing in an expert to train several members of staff in key advanced skills relevant to their work will be an appropriate, efficient, and effective way of moving forward (and this was requested by staff as shown above). This can only be identified on the ground, but satisfying this latent demand is looking urgent. Staff are signalling readiness to modernise how we work, if we invest in them.

Strategic improvement in training will directly enable:

- The UK Data Service Strategy 2024–2030.
- National priorities around data interoperability and responsible AI.
- Efficiency and resilience in core UK Data Service operations.

The skills requested align strongly with external expectations from the ESRC and UKRI and government regarding digital maturity and automation.

To meet staff needs and achieve our strategic goals, as a Data Service we will need to:

1. Move from ad-hoc courses to structured development pathways, responding to clusters of need. Pathways need to be foundational and orienteering for some, but take others to highly specialist/expert levels.
2. Ensure training supports immediate application to people's active and routine work, not just knowledge acquisition. Training must be experiential.
3. Introduce AI-assisted workflow pilots, with commensurate training, to respond to staff expressed needs.
4. Develop reproducible workflow standards with commensurate training for relevant staff.
5. Build capability in managers to lead confidently in a digital and AI-enabled environment, especially when the technical skills of their staff well exceed their own.

These issues are strategic and operational matters for the UK Data Service Directors and Senior Leadership to take forward.

How do staff expect training will benefit them?

The free text data was analysed qualitatively for common meaning and key themes emerging. The Table below shows what respondents hope to gain from enhancing their computational and data skills. Of the 64 respondents, two did not answer the question and one thought there would be no benefit, but the remaining 61 mentioned many foreseeable benefits. There were no clear differences between managers and staff.

Table 9: Themes from free text data

Theme	% of respondents mentioning	Examples of responses
Upskill knowledge/enhanced analytical capability/innovation	62%	"as someone with zero experience, it will help me to understand the service we offer and the kinds of queries our users have"; "with the increased use of AI, I need to upskill my knowledge"; "in the face of cloud computing migration, it would be nice to know how the various AWS services work"; "improve my own computational skills useful to create training resources"; "enhances my ability to design, implement and optimize AI driven solution"; "in terms of web dev and UX skills, I think these could point us in new directions for the UKDS website"; "enable me to ... provide innovative solutions for the analysis of large datasets"
Efficiency/ productivity	48%	"being able to understand and plan future demand for computing sources and managing it efficiently is a must in the cloud computing"; "given the resource-intensive nature of [ANON], this is vital to help improve

		efficiency”; “developing a deeper understanding of SQL and data management will greatly enhance the speed and efficiency of automation and data processing tasks”; “allow me to complete my assigned tasks more quickly and free me up to focus on different tasks”; “to efficiently ingest and process data, automate the flow and reduce manual intervention”
Modern methods/keep with new technologies	41%	“would be useful to have more modern management methods”, “if researchers use more computational tools and methods, I need to understand the software and methods”; “since these technologies evolve so quickly... quality training ... can further improve the quality of my work”; “the world of data is constantly evolving and keeping up with these developments is essential in order to maintain the high standards expected from the research community for the UK Data Service”; “as the future of [ANON] evolves, these skills will be crucial in adapting to decentralised data formats, ensuring that users can navigate the data effectively”
Better service to users and stakeholders	29%	“it’s what many of our users want and need”; “essential in order to maintain the high standards expected from the research community for the UK Data Service”; “prepare me to continue to provide high quality support in a rapidly changing data landscape”; “being able to talk in an informed way with potential users/customers”; “further our understanding of what our data creators work with ... for their own data management pipelines”; “we need to be aware of what our users might be doing”; “vital I understand more about how researchers use computational methods”; “knowledge of virtual environments and interactive coding skills could lead to big improvements in the delivery of training – have existing skills but improving them would have a big impact”
Quality and reproducibility	22%	“...ultimately improving the quality of instructional materials and workflows”; “help with automation of processes”; “improve our work quality and keep us providing the most up do data services”; “to efficiently ingest and process data, automate the flow and reduce manual intervention”; “to continue to provide high quality support in a rapidly changing data landscape”
Risk management/best practice	21%	“it would help me to learn more about how to prevent data breaches”; “to learn more about best security and development practices so that it makes work safer/more efficient”; “being able to accessibility check

		documents more easily and keep up to date with chances to accessibility standards...”; “would enable more functionality for our services and improve security”
Collaboration and reporting	14%	“make better clearer reports, dashboards etc”; “help improve tools and teach others how to use them in their research workflows”; “automating reports, collecting data, creating reminders, document management, minutes for meetings..”; “more in-depth engagement with project topics and teams”; “better deliver management information and KPIs”

A number of implications arise from this analysis:

1. **Strong motivation to upskill and adapt:** Almost all respondents (61 of 64) articulated clear, concrete benefits from training; only one person thought there would be no benefit. The most frequent expectation (mentioned by 62%) is *enhanced capability and innovation* – staff want to build deeper understanding of data systems, AI, coding, computational analysis, technology stacks, cloud technologies etc, so they can contribute more effectively to service delivery and development. This indicates a workforce that is highly motivated to learn, and sees upskilling as essential to professional competence, not an optional extra.
2. **Efficiency and productivity are central:** Nearly half (48%) of respondents explicitly link training to working more efficiently – e.g. through automation, faster data processing, or freeing time for more strategic work. Staff view computational training as a route to ‘doing more with less’, reflecting both pride in service delivery and realism about resource constraints.
3. **Anticipating rapid technological change:** 41% mention *keeping up with modern methods and emerging technologies*, especially AI, automation, and decentralised data formats. Training is thus seen as a means of future-proofing both individual skills and the Service’s collective capability, in a fast-evolving digital environment.
4. **Quality, reproducibility, and best practice:** around one-fifth of respondents explicitly refer to quality assurance, risk management, or reproducibility. Staff want to align their work with recognised best practices in data ethics, security, and reproducible workflows. This shows that professional standards are widely valued and that there is appetite for training that embeds good data governance and responsible practice.
5. **Enhanced service to users and stakeholders:** nearly a third (29%) highlight benefits in supporting external researchers and data users. Staff link their own technical skills to improving the quality, responsiveness, and credibility of user-facing services. This reinforces the strong service identity within the UK Data Service.
6. **Collaboration and communication benefits:** although less frequent (14%), several respondents mention improved reporting, teamwork, and knowledge sharing as

anticipated benefits. This suggests a recognition that upskilling can enhance internal communication and coordination, not just technical execution.

This survey has demonstrated that staff see training as a way to become more capable, efficient, and future-ready professionals who deliver higher quality, more responsive data services. Their expectations are constructive and forward-looking.

Following from this:

1. Staff already perceive clear benefits and see training as key to success. Framing it as strategic investment in capability (rather than correcting a deficit) should sustain engagement and morale.
2. It emerges as important to design training that connects efficiency and innovation. Modules should show how new tools directly reduce manual work and improve quality — reinforcing the link between innovation and productivity.
3. Staff are alert to risks and standards; training in these areas will meet real demand with the potential to strengthen compliance and credibility.
4. For maximum impact, connect training goals to improved user experience and public value as these are the outcomes staff themselves identify.

Key insights and recommendations

1. There is a clear, organisation-wide mandate for computational and AI capability.

Staff across every role type including technical, user-facing, and operational, recognise that computational skills are essential to the future of the Service. This alignment across the workforce provides a very strong foundation for collective upskilling.

2. Skills are valued but unevenly distributed, creating capability gaps and operational risk.

While some teams already work intensively with programming, cloud tools, automation and reproducible workflows, many staff have limited opportunities or skills to apply these methods.

3. Demand for training reflects a desire for practical transformation.

Staff want to apply AI, automation, reproducibility, and coding directly to their existing workloads. The most commonly requested skill areas (AI/ML, prompt engineering, Python/R, SQL, workflow automation, and cloud architecture) are central to modernising our operations and meeting external expectations.

4. Training needs differ substantially by role, meaning a single generic offer will not work.
-

Technical teams need advanced skills in cloud, architecture, APIs, metadata/ontologies, and security. User-facing teams want automation, data visualisation, analytical literacy, and applied AI. Non-data roles seek entry-level computational skills to modernise administrative tasks. Managers require digital leadership capability.

The Service has multiple learner personas; training must be structured around them.

5. Staff are motivated, future-focused, and ready to learn, but need guidance and pathways.

Many respondents expressed uncertainty about where to begin or how to progress. Without structured pathways and visible progression, there is a risk that motivation will dissipate and organisational opportunity will be lost.

6. Training is strongly linked to productivity, reproducibility and service quality.

Staff associate training with faster workflows, reduced manual effort, improved user support, higher quality standards, and better risk management. Upskilling will therefore deliver direct service gains, not just individual development.

7. This is as much a leadership and organisational design issue as a training issue.

The survey shows that effective use of data, automation and AI depends on shared standards, leadership confidence, team-level practices and organisational permission to change how work is done. Training alone will not deliver transformation unless it is accompanied by clear leadership signals, shared expectations and structural support.

Recommendations

1. Develop structured, role-differentiated skills pathways. Pathways should support:
 - Foundation skills for operational and non-data roles.
 - Applied analytical and AI-assisted skills for user-facing teams.
 - Specialist cloud, architecture and reproducibility skills for processing/infrastructure roles.
 - Digital leadership and governance capability for managers.
2. But it is important to ensure training is practical, contextual and work-integrated. Staff emphasised that training must be immediately applicable to their actual workloads. This means a need to therefore:
 - Prioritise task-based learning.
 - Use real UK Data Service datasets and processes.
 - Build training around service-specific problems.
 - Use expert-led sessions to guide teams through real workflow improvements.

3. Invest in automation, reproducibility and AI-assisted workflow pilots. Staff specifically requested automation of repeat tasks and support for AI-enabled working. Pilots should be designed to reduce manual labour, demonstrate value quickly, and provide replicable templates for wider implementation.
4. Introduce organisation-wide standards for reproducible workflows and data governance both to address strategic priorities and staff demand. This means creating guidance and training on version control, APIs, documentation, metadata standards, and cloud-based reproducibility.
5. Develop an operational plan for how to provide the support that people need. Many respondents requested team-based expert support. This points to a need for some capacity – internal or external – that could allow teams to gain applied, contextualised help that generic courses cannot provide.
6. Develop Directorate-level training plans to ensure alignment with operational reality. While this report cannot disaggregate by Directorate, the pattern of need will differ across teams. Each Directorate should assess its workforce’s position, define local priorities and develop training pathways for roles within their teams. This should be an ongoing process for managers at all levels.
7. Frame investment as capability-building, not deficit remediation. Staff already see clear benefits and are highly motivated. Positioning training as strategic investment in the future of the UK Data Service will maintain engagement and support organisational culture change.
8. Assign senior level ownership and clear accountability for computational capability and training plans. To ensure momentum is sustained, responsibility for overseeing skills pathways, standards, and applied capability development should sit clearly with senior leadership. Without explicit ownership, there is a risk that responsibility diffuses to individuals and teams, reproducing the uneven capability that staff have here identified as a concern.
9. These findings are likely to have wider implications for other data services nationally, and internationally. The results will be of interest for the ESRC Future Data Service team with reference to the [Phase 1 report](#) recommendation to invest in the *People, Organisation and Cultures* within data infrastructures (Welpton et al, 2025). It will also be of interest to similar initiatives across other UKRI funding councils.

In conclusion, this survey demonstrates that the UK Data Service has a motivated, reflective and future-oriented workforce that recognises the necessity of computational, automated, and AI-enabled working. Staff are not asking for abstract skills, but for the capabilities to do their jobs differently, and better. The challenge is now organisational: to provide the leadership, structure, investment and budget required to convert this readiness into durable, service-wide

transformation. How to resource this sustainably will be a key question, as will how to measure and monitor progress against objectives. If addressed strategically, this represents a significant opportunity to strengthen the UK Data Service's resilience, effectiveness and standing as part of our national data infrastructure.

References

Welpton, R., Dutton, K., Wilson, R., & Hutchins, B. (2025). Future Data Services Phase 1: Fixing the Data Pipeline (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17351345>

Appendix:

Survey Questions

1. Practical questions (bot-check)
Please complete the following bot-check

If you are happy to participate, please complete the questions below and make sure you have read through the Participant Information Sheet and the consent form.

2. PIS (checkbox)
I confirm that I have read the attached Participant Information Sheet (Version 3, Date 26/11/2024) for the survey and have had the opportunity to consider the information and ask questions and had these answered satisfactorily.
Yes
3. Consent (checkbox)
I confirm that I have read and agree to the attached consent form for the survey.
Yes

About the survey

Please note that this survey pertains to skills that we anticipate will become important for the effective delivery of future data services. Therefore, this is not a professional evaluation of your current skills or job performance. Your answers will not be used against you or as a criticism of your current abilities. Rather, we would like to gauge any computational skills gaps as we look forward to an evolving data landscape and provide opportunities for training where possible. As the data landscape continues to evolve many of you will have heard growing buzz around new topics such as machine learning, big data, and AI. Computational skills ranging from advanced computing techniques to computational social science are likely to become increasingly important for effectively delivering data services and supporting cutting-edge research.

Please tell us a bit about yourself/ Contact details

We're asking for your details so that we can contact you to organise any training that you may request later in this survey. Your details will not be shared with anyone outside of the research team apart from your manager/team lead/department lead who may review your answers. This will be done solely to help identify relevant training opportunities, not to evaluate your job performance.

4. Practical questions (short free-text)
Please enter your name.
 5. Practical questions (short free-text)
Please enter your email address.
 6. Practical questions (multiple choice, with long free-text 'Other' option)
Which part of the UK Data Service do you work for? Choose more than one if it applies.
-

Essex Business Strategy and Operations, Essex Comms and Engagement, Essex Data Operations (Access, Training and User Support, Data Curation and Publishing, Collections Development and Producer Relations), Essex Tech Services, CMI, EDINA, JISC, UCL, Other (please specify)

These questions focus on your current role and your familiarity with computational methods or skills. We'd like to know whether you feel they would be useful in your current role.

What do we mean by computational skills?

In this survey, "computational skills" refers to advanced, emerging skills and tools that go beyond standard statistical packages such as SPSS and Stata. We're focusing on newer, more adaptable methods that involve programming languages (such as R or Python), machine learning, artificial intelligence, and other techniques designed to enhance data analysis, automation, and problem-solving capabilities in innovative ways. The goal is to identify training needs in these areas to better support future data service requirements.

7. Future expectations (Likert scale)

To what extent do you agree with the following statement: "Computational skills will be essential for effective data services in the future"?

Strongly agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, Strongly disagree.

8. Current skills (multiple choice, with long free-text 'Other' option)

Which of the following computational skills or methods do you currently use in your role? These skills do not pertain to SPSS or Stata. Please select all that apply.

Programming languages (e.g. Python, R, SQL, JavaScript), Machine learning, Artificial intelligence (e.g. natural language processing, predictive modelling), Data wrangling/cleaning, Data visualisation, Workflow automation (e.g. Excel macros, Alteryx, Zapier), Cloud computing platforms (e.g. AWS, Google Cloud), Version control (e.g. Git, GitHub), Big data processing (e.g. Hadoop, Spark), Prompt engineering (e.g. with Chat-GPT), Making API requests, Other (please specify), None

9. Current skills (multiple choice, only appears if programming was a skill selected in the previous question)

What is the highest level of proficiency you have in programming languages (e.g. Python, R) commonly used for computational tasks?

Beginner, Intermediate, Advanced

10. Current skills (multiple choice)

How often do you currently use computational skills or methods in your role?

Daily, Weekly, Monthly, Rarely, Never

11. Future expectations (multiple choice)

Do you think learning new computational skills would be useful for your role? You can select more than one option if it applies.

Yes, it'd be useful for my role now, Yes, it'd be useful for my role in the future, No, Don't know.

We'd now like to know whether there is any training you would like to request

We have a **new UKRI grant to upskill UKDS staff** in computational skills to enhance data service capacity. We will do this via external training courses or commissioned training from external providers, so we need to know which training topics would benefit you. This is your opportunity to identify training needs, put forward options for training to pursue and request funding for training!

12. Training demand (multiple choice)

Would you like to receive any training in computational skills that would be relevant to your job?

Yes, No, Not sure.

13. Training demand (long free text)

What is the topic(s) of the training that you would like to receive? Be as general or specific as you want.

14. Future expectations (long free text)

Why do you think training in this topic would benefit your role? In a few words.

15. Training demand (long free text)

Do you have any specific training courses or training providers in mind? If so, please add the link or name here. You can find some examples here ([link](#)).

16. Training demand (multiple choice, with long free text 'Other' option)

What training format do you prefer? For instance, some people prefer a structured event whereas others may prefer to use online learning materials where they are able to go at their own pace. Tick all that apply.

Training event (in person), Training event (online), Online learning materials, Bringing in an expert to guide teams/individuals, Other (Please specify)

17. Practical questions (multiple choice)

Are you willing and able to participate in this training in the first half of 2025?

Yes, No

UKDS Managers/team leads/department leads

We'd now like to know from our UKDS managers/team leads/departments lead if there are any training topics that they think would benefit their team members. If you are not a manager/team lead/department lead you can simply select 'No' and proceed to the final section of the survey.

18. Practical questions (multiple choice)

Are you a manager/team lead/department lead of a UKDS team?

Yes, No

19. Training demand (long free text, only appears if 'Yes' selected in the previous question)

Are there any topics of training that you think your team would benefit from? Be as general or specific as you want. Please include your team name.

20. Practical questions (multiple choice)

Would you be willing to take part in impact interviews about the training you attend?

Yes, No

21. Training demand (long free text)

Do you have any other comments about computational skills training needs in the UKDS?

Stop Words

Words NVivo automatically includes in stop words for word cloud formation, plus bold words added to remove words that were frequent but uninformative.

different directly do does doesn't doesn't doing don't don't down during each etc **example**
experience few following for from further had hadn't hadn't has hasn't hasn't have haven't
haven't having he he'd he'll he's he'd he'll her here here's here's hers herself he's him himself
his how how's how's i i'd i'll i'm i've i'd if i'll i'm in into is isn't isn't it it's its it's itself i've know
learn learning let's let's like mainly me more **moreover** most must mustn't mustn't my myself
need needs no nor not of off on once only or other ought our ours ourselves out outside over
own please **possibly receive role** said same say says shall shan't shan't she she'd she'll
she's she'd she'll she's should shouldn't shouldn't **skills** so some such terms than that that's
that's the their theirs them themselves then there there's there's these they they'd they'll
they're they've they'd they'll they're they've things this those though through to too **topics**
training under until up upon us **use useful using** very was wasn't wasn't we we'd we'll we're
we've we'd well we'll were we're weren't weren't we've what what's what's when when's
when's where where's where's which while who who's whom who's whose why why's why's
will with won't won't work would wouldn't wouldn't you you'd you'll you're you've you'd you'll
your you're yours yourself yourselves you've

Codebook

Codes

Codes\\Survey coding

One folder per open ended question

Codes\\Survey coding\\training_topics_DI

Training topics identified

Name	Description	Files	References
AI and Machine Learning	Training requests relating to artificial intelligence, machine learning, generative AI, or applying AI tools (e.g. ChatGPT, Copilot) to automate tasks, improve workflows, and analyse data. Includes interest in AI ethics, bias mitigation and staying current with rapidly evolving AI techniques. (Includes free text like “AI / ML”, “generative AI”, “Machine Learning mainly LLM”.)	1	26
APIs and Data Integration	Mentions of using or building Application Programming Interfaces to connect systems, automate data retrieval, to automate data movement between systems, integrate datasets across platform, or integrate multiple tools/platforms together. (Examples include: “Workflow automation, API’s, Machine learning” and interest in programming languages for API use.)	1	4
Automation	Desire to automate repetitive or manual tasks (e.g. macros, scripts, workflow automation, data pipelines). Encompasses automation using Excel/Word macros, Python, cloud tools, or AI-driven automation; also digitalisation.	1	16

Name	Description	Files	References
Big Data	Interest in analysing or understanding large, complex, or unstructured datasets, including neural networks and algorithms used in data-intensive environments.	1	2
Neural networks, SNA, classification algorithms	Specific analytic methods (SNA, neural nets, classification models). Usually part of broader ML-oriented requests.	1	3
Text analysis	Specific interest in analysing text (feedback form analysis, using LLMs for text, or coding text data).	1	3
Data Security	Training requests relating to security, governance, information security, and risks around data handling, particularly in relation to AI deployment.	1	4
Data Visualisation	How to visualise data (PowerBI, Tableau, Looker Studio, infographics), including user-centred visualisation and presenting insights clearly.	1	8
Database Design, Data Architecture and Management	Understanding how data is structured, stored, accessed and linked — including data warehousing, data lakes, SQL, metadata, cloud-based data setups, and database modelling. Or focuses specifically on database tools, schema design, SQL, SPARQL, Cloud/AWS/Azure setup, DuckDB, and other database environments. (Multiple entries mention SQL, cloud infrastructure, and data warehouse management)	1	17
Ethical Issues and Data Governance	Understanding ethical issues and governance around AI or data handling — including bias, explainability, responsible use.	1	2
Full stack application development	Building and deploying applications end-to-end, often on cloud infrastructure, including	1	7

Name	Description	Files	References
	DevOps, frontend development, and running applications.		
Geospatial analysis	Using tools and data methods for spatial/geographic analysis and mapping.	1	3
Metadata, Semantics and Ontologies, Interoperability	How to make data interoperable, machine-readable, or discoverable; RDF; Ontologies and taxonomies; Controlled vocabularies; Linked data; Semantic web standards; Schema.org, OWL, SPARQL, SKOS, etc.	1	6
Need help to understand what I don't know	People expressing uncertainty about which training they need; desire for an overview of possible computational skills and where to start. Includes requests for beginner-friendly orientation.	1	8
Prompt Engineering and LLMs	Learning how to write effective prompts, work with large language models (LLMs), and integrate AI into everyday tasks. Includes requests for guidance on how to use AI tools well, limitations, responsible use, and how AI can support analysis or administrative tasks. (Includes "Prompt engineering", and multiple requests for using Copilot / ChatGPT in workflows.)	1	25
Python, R, other coding languages	Specific requests for Python or R. Training to learn or improve programming skills, including reproducibility, version control, and collaborative workflows (Git). Requests often about moving beyond Excel, automating tasks, and scaling analysis.	1	20
Qualitative data_NVivo	Requests for training in qualitative analysis, and specifically for using NVivo.	1	2
Statistical analysis skills	Requests for statistical analysis and methods training (including advanced or computational statistics, not just basic stats).	1	3

Name	Description	Files	References
UX, website development, accessibility	Front-end development, user-experience design, accessibility standards, improving websites or user interfaces.	1	7
Workflow Reproducibility	Reproducible and automated workflows (Git/version control, virtual environments, scripting, collaborative coding). Also training in project management specifically for data or computational projects (planning, managing technical workflows, scoping technical work).	1	13